

KARAKALPAK SAUKELE

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Annotation: *Karakalpak women's wedding saukele headdresses are an example of the high level of work of folk craftsmen - jewellers and embroiderers, as well as evidence of original spiritual and handicraft traditions of Karakalpaks, revealing features of ritual and ceremonial practices. The article compares these artefacts for the first time and identifies their parallels and differences. Until recently, seven unique samples of saukele were known to exist. All of them are kept in museum collections. The Karakalpak saukele, a helmet-like headdress, an integral part of a girl's ritual wedding dress, decorated with jewellery and embroidery, is a valuable source of information about the worldview of the steppe people.*

Keywords: *karakalpaks, saukele, kiymesek, totem, cloth, zhyga, kyran, saukele burshak, boydasy, tobelik, alaka.*

At the heart of a saukele is a hemispherical cap (tumak) with earflaps, felted inside, woven outside and additionally decorated with a plait and long embroidered strips of cloth (halka or alaka) with fringe at the end. The hat is embroidered in some places, stamped figured copper-silver plates with inserts of corals and turquoise are sewn on the sides, the front forehead is decorated with coral beads of different sizes. According to T.A. Zhdanko, the genesis of Karakalpak saukele is connected with fighting helmets of women-warriors of Sako-Massaget and Sarmato-Alanian tribes, which were known to have extremely strong traditions of matriarchy (Zhdanko 1964: 4.)

Similar helmet-shaped headdresses (both male and female), judging by archaeological finds, were widespread in the territory of the Altai Mountains (Pazyryk barrows, Ukok Plateau) and Priaralie (Levina 1968: 173) already in ^{^^} c. BC.

One more parallel is traced from numismatic data: high headdress of Parthian king Sinatruk is one of the symbols of power depicted on drachma of 77-70 B.C. It is decorated with three rows of beads and has undoubted similarity with the headdress of Karakalpak women. The helmet-shaped headdress of a king on one of the Khorezmian coins of the 1st c. B.C. in the

image material from Urartu is also similar to the saukele headdress (Tolstoy 1952: 15; Morozova 1963: 188).

The Spanish ambassador to the court of Timur (Tamerlane) Gonzalez de Clavijo, describing his wife's headdress, noted: "On her head, like a helmet of red cloth, similar to those in which they fight [...], this helmet was very high and on it were many large bright and round pearls, many rubies and turquoise, and various other stones, very beautifully set in..." (Abdullah et al. 1986. (Abdullayev et al. 1986).

In the diary of the members of the Russian embassy, Lieutenant D. Gladyshev and surveyor I. Muravin, who visited the Karakalpaks in 1740, there is a description of a headdress called kasava, similar to saukele. They write: "Their wives wear the same as the Kirgiz, only their kasavs are made of copper, tinned with silver, and others have silver ones; also on top of them are made small ears, and in these ears are inserted stones, more marian; They also have small cones sewn on the linen cloth, which they put under the scarf; and between the cones they put a little white calico and uramal, and tie it under the beard, and hang it down the same way as Kirghiz kasines; and braids are curled in the same manner" (Journey... 1851: 70). .. 1851: 70).

In form, materials and system of decoration, the surviving examples of the Karakalpak saukele are close to the headdresses of the Chuvash, Mari, Mordva, Udmurts, Bashkirs and Kirghiz kep takyas. They also have similarities with the head-dresses of the Kazakh and Turkmen women, each of which had its own differences.

According to A.S. Morozova, from helmets of warriors to the headdresses of priests and kings with the following transformation into an everyday headdress, this is the evolution of helmet-like attire that was distributed across a vast territory from Western Asia across the Caucasus, Amu Darya valley and Transcaspian lowland to the Sako-Scythian steppes, far to the north-east (Morozova 1963: 134). Mention of the saukele as a part of the military accoutrement is mentioned, in particular, in a famous Karakalpak epos "Kyrk-kyz" ("Forty girls"): the leader of Amazons, Gulaim, wears this headdress.

There is another opinion. For example, H. E. Esbergenov suggests that the Karakalpak saukele originally only had a cult and ceremonial purpose throughout the time of its existence and continued to be used as a symbol of ritual female Karakalpak costume up to the 20th century (Esbergenov 1999: 102).

Mention of saukele during wedding celebrations can be found in many authors. During preparations to leave for the groom's house a Karakalpak bride "was dressed in wedding clothes, zhetsge [wife of her elder brother] braided the bride's hair into two braids and put on a wedding cloak - kyzyl kiymeshek, saukele (Esbergenov and Atamuratov 1975: 82). Until the beginning of the 20th century this ritual was an integral part of a Karakalpak wedding, and later saukele not only disappeared from use but also physically (except for the samples under consideration).

Saukele was more widespread among Karakalpak Kungrats living along the southern coast of the Aral Sea from Kuskanatau-Zair (Chimbay region) to Madeli (settlement Porlytau of Muynak region) (Ethnography of Karakalpaks... 1980: 95). Unfortunately, there is no exact data about specific places of origin of the preserved saukele or about their former owners; even the fact that one of them was bought by the expedition in 1961 in the Togyzterek tract (near Kazakhdaria) does not specify the place of its creation. As the steppe nations migrated, so did the objects created by them.

Revolutionary and post-revolutionary years of the twentieth century forced the owners of the saukele to part with it or separately with its jewelled parts. Time, in turn, inexorably destroyed woven and felted basis of this headdress. However, individual jewellery parts are still carefully preserved in some families.

According to M.S. Andreev and O.A. Sukhareva, the name saukele comes from a combination of two words: sau and kele. Sau (seu) comes from Iranian shah 'king'. (Sukhareva 1954: 339). As to the kel part, some authors derive it from Iranian kalé "head", or kul (from kolal). So, saukele 'the king's hat'. Along with saukele is consonant a Turkic (Tatar) word combination sau ku len (lit. "a healthy daughter-in-law"), which may also reflect the sense of the name of this religious or ceremonial headdress. A literal translation of the word saukele from Karakalpak means "whole, protected" (sau) "head" (kelle), which recalls the connection of this attire with the ancient military helmets.

Another interpretation of this word is offered by E.V. Rtveladze, who believes that the name saukele is derived from Old Khorezmian or Sogdian sau 'black' and kalá, kele 'head'. This version, along with others, probably reveals the etymology of the word Karakalpak. E.V. Rtveladze also notes that also.

the last king of Khorezm, who ruled Fig. 3. the crosshairs on tumak saukele (priv. in the 10th c. ^^ was called Shau (sau) Shafash.) Photo by the

author (published for the first time) which is also consonant with the word "black". The semantic content of the headdress is equally complex and multifaceted. Analysis of its components allows assuming that the form of saukele symbolically combines elements of three spheres: water, earth and heaven. Thus, corals, the gifts of the sea, address us to the water element.

These beads used in the past for embroidering the saukele were brought to Central Asia, possibly from the Mediterranean (Spain, France, Algeria, Tunisia and Turkey) or from India and China; hence they were very rare and exotic. Metal patches of silver with gilding and turquoise indicate a connection of the headwear with the earth. Turquoise was of local origin as this mineral had been mined in Central Asia (in what is now Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan) for more than 2000 years; it is also possible that it could have been imported from Iran (Nishapur) and China (Sichuan and Manchuria), about which there are mentions in the diaries of Marco Polo, a famous traveler.

The domed shape of the saukele refers in turn to the heavenly sphere, as do some of the patches, in particular the cross-shaped tumak element understood as a solar sign. Divided into four parts by means of a broad black cross, the headdress is perceived as a symbol of the heavenly dome, an embodiment of protection and patronage. Therefore the headdress expresses the idea of interrelation of water, earth and cosmos in the environment of various protective symbols, the role of which is played by the embroidery motifs and jewellery.

The decor of the embroidery is dominated by the motif of the cross. It should be noted that the cross with its variants (arrow or cross-shaped endings) is one of the most common elements in the products of Karakalpak craftsmen, including saukele. Cross-shaped figures are familiar from as early as Neolithic ceramics. as early as the Neolithic Era.

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